

Mendelian randomization study on vitamin C and the risk of ischemic stroke may be misleading

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Comment on:

Martens LG, Luo J, Willems van Dijk K, Jukema JW, Noordam R, van Heemst D.
Diet-Derived Antioxidants Do Not Decrease Risk of Ischemic Stroke: A Mendelian Randomization Study in 1 Million People.

J Am Heart Assoc. 2021 Dec 7;10(23):e022567.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34796734>

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Martens et al. concluded that their Mendelian randomization study that among several antioxidants, vitamin C was not “causally associated with a lower risk of ischemic stroke” [1].

The Martens et al. study was based on an earlier study, which reported that “the variance of plasma vitamin C explained by the 11 lead SNPs was 1.87% on average” [2, p 102]. However, Martens et al did not give any consideration to the plasma vitamin C levels that their Mendelian randomization study would correspond to.

From the 1.87% explanation of variance, and the data about the plasma vitamin C means and SD levels available in the earlier paper [2], we calculated that the 11 SNPs would correspond to the comparison of two population groups of equal size with vitamin C levels of 47.3 vs. 52.7 μM [3]. Such a comparison is not clinically meaningful.

With low dietary vitamin C intakes, plasma levels can fall below 10 μM , whereas with high dietary intakes, plasma levels can increase to over 80 μM (see Fig. 1C in [4]). It is important to take into account this eightfold range of plasma vitamin C levels when considering the dose-health relationship in the community, but that was not done by Martens et al. [1].

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

Low plasma vitamin C levels are not uncommon. Levels below 11 μM were reported, for example, in 25% of men and 16% of women from low-income populations in the UK [5], and in 13% of a US cohort [6]. In many population groups in less developed countries, such low vitamin C levels are even more common [7]. Thus, large segments of the population have vitamin C levels that are less than one fifth of the “low” plasma vitamin C level corresponding to the Martens et al. analysis.

Based on the large variation in the plasma levels of vitamin C in the population, the most relevant comparison is between low and high plasma levels, e.g., 10–20 μM vs. 60–100 μM . If a study compares small variations within the high intake range only, such as 47.3 vs. 52.7 μM , the comparison is uninformative about possible effects of vitamin C in the low intake range.

Vitamin C may, or may not, influence the risk of ischemic stroke. However, the study by Martens et al. is not informative about whether the risk is increased with plasma levels in the 10-20 μM range, compared with higher levels.

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